

The Impact of Seasonality on the Handicraft Market in India: A Google Trend Analysis

Yuthika Goel

Abstract

This research investigates the seasonal dynamics of the traditional clothing and handicraft market, focusing on four distinct clothing types—Onam saree, Veshti, Langa Voni, and Pattu Pavadai—prevalent in southern India. In response to the evolving landscape of consumer preferences and the socio-economic significance of the handicraft industry, this study aims to unravel the patterns of demand and seasonality within the market. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the research combines quantitative data from Google Trend searches with qualitative insights over a two-year post-Covid-19 period. Time series analysis is applied to understand the impact of cultural festivals and seasonal variations on fashion preferences, utilizing over 100 search queries for each clothing type. The findings unveil distinct patterns in the demand for the selected clothing types, predominantly influenced by cultural festivals and traditions. While Onam saree experiences a significant peak during the festival season, Veshti maintains consistent popularity year-round, with peaks during the festival of Puratasi. Langa Voni, deeply rooted in cultural traditions, sustains high search results year-round, peaking during the Vijay Dashmi celebrations. Pattu Pavadai, although exhibiting lower overall search volumes, sees a surge in July, aligned with the Puratasi festival. This research holds significance for stakeholders in the traditional clothing and handicraft industry, offering actionable insights for producers to align their production and marketing strategies effectively. Furthermore, the study contributes to the broader discourse on the socio-economic impact of traditional crafts, emphasising the importance of preserving cultural heritage while adapting to evolving consumer preferences in southern India.

Keywords: Traditional clothing, Handicraft market, Seasonal variations, Cultural festivals, Consumer behaviour.

1. Introduction

The world is a diverse tapestry of cultures, each weaving its unique fabric of traditions, customs, and arts. One significant aspect that reflects this cultural richness is traditional clothing and handicrafts. These elements not only showcase the creativity of a community but also contribute to the socio-economic dynamics of a region. This discussion delves into the global and Indian perspectives of traditional clothing, with a focus on the handicraft market. By exploring the data surrounding this market, the aim is to understand its impact on employment and economics. The handicraft industry is an important source of income for rural areas, employing over 6 million craftspeople, many of whom are women and members of the socially disadvantaged [1]. Today India is a significant manufacturer and exporter of handicrafts worldwide. There are almost 35,000 products available in the nation’s 744 handicraft clusters, which employ nearly 212,000 craftspeople. [1] The handicraft industry in India is dominated by female artisans with over 56% of the total artisans [2].

Source: Export Promotion Council for Handicrafts (EPCH)

Figure 1 : Country wise share of India’s handicraft exports [2]

Traditional clothing serves as a visual expression of cultural identity, representing centuries-old practices and heritage and is a testament to the diversity of human civilization. The handicraft market, closely tied to traditional attire, encompasses a wide range of artisanal

products such as pottery, jewellery, textiles, and more. This market not only preserves cultural heritage but also acts as a source of livelihood for numerous skilled artisans.

1.1 Handicraft Market

The global handicraft market size is projected to grow from \$1,007.07 billion in 2023 to \$1,972.32 billion by 2030, at a CAGR of 10.08% [3]. The India handicrafts market size reached US\$ 3,968.0 Million in 2022. It is expected that the market will reach US\$ 6,218.4 Million by 2028, exhibiting a growth rate (CAGR) of 7.7% during 2023-2028. [4]. The vast range of handicrafts manufactured in India are shown below:

Figure 2: Handicraft map of India [5]

The lifestyle of consumers is changing and so are their tastes. As this sector is unorganised and is spread across the length and breadth of the country, the artisans tend to continue to create or produce their wares based on their experience, oblivion of the fact that products need to be modified to remain contemporary [6]. Therefore, the impact of seasonality on the

handicraft market is significant. Understanding the patterns of seasonality is crucial for both artisans and stakeholders in the industry. This enables artisans to create seasonal collections that are relevant to customers' needs and align with the corresponding festivities, holidays, or weather conditions [7]. A surge in demand during specific seasons can provide opportunities for increased income, but it also poses challenges related to production capacity and meeting market demands. Conversely, a decrease in demand during certain seasons may affect the economic stability of artisans.

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from Google Trend searches for four clothing types over a two-year post-Covid-19 period. Time series analysis was applied to identify patterns and trends, focusing on seasonal variations. The goal was to understand the dynamics influencing fashion preferences, with over 100 search queries for each clothing type supporting robust data collection. This is a suitable method of data collection since Google Trends is an incredibly powerful tool for marketers to gain valuable insights into their target audience, track trending topics, and stay ahead of the competition. By using this dynamic tool, businesses can analyze search data to gain an understanding of consumer behavior, understand seasonal patterns, and identify popular topics in their industry [8]. The study analyzes the popularity trends of four specific clothing types—Onam saree, Veshti, Langa Voni, and Pattu Pavadai—over a three-year period. For Onam saree, searches peak in July due to the Onam festival, making it seasonally popular, with concentrated interest in Kerala, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu, and Karnataka. Veshti remains popular year-round, experiencing peaks in October, coinciding with the festival of Puratasi. Regionally, Veshti searches are concentrated in Puducherry, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala. Langa Voni consistently maintains high search results, peaking in October and September, aligning with the festival of Puratasi. Region-wise, searches for Langa Voni are concentrated in Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, and Kerala. Pattu Pavadai shows lower year-round demand but experiences a peak in July, especially in Kerala, Tamil Nadu, and Puducherry, coinciding with the Puratasi festival. Producers are advised to adjust production based on these seasonal and regional popularity trends.

2. Methodology

The aim of this paper is to understand the seasonality in the Indian Handicraft market for understanding how to maximise an artisan's revenue and minimise seasonal unemployment in the states of southern India. The conducted experiment employed a mixed methodology

approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methods to comprehensively analyse the popularity trends of four specific clothing types (Langa Voni, Pattu Padavai, Onam saree, and Veshti) over a two-year period post-Covid-19. Google trend search results served as the primary quantitative data source, offering insights into the relative interest or search volume for the selected clothing items. This methodology is effective because 85% of online consumers take a product-related action within 24 hours of discovering a product that meets their needs [9].

Subsequent time series analysis was applied to discern patterns and trends in the data, particularly focusing on seasonal variations. The objective was not only to identify when certain clothing items gained popularity in specific states but also to infer the reasons behind these fluctuations. This approach aimed to provide a nuanced understanding of the dynamics influencing the fashion preferences of the target audience during the specified post-pandemic timeframe. Each clothing type had 100+ search queries making this a suitable methodology for data collection.

3. Results

The search results for Onam saree in Figure 3 over a period of 3 years are shown on the graph above. The searches remain dominant during most part of the year but the searches peak during the month of July due to the arrival of the festival of Onam which is celebrated during August or September [10]. This implies the sales would have hiked in this season as well

making it a seasonally popular product.

Figure 3: Search results for Onam saree over 3 years

Figure 4: Search results for Onam saree region wise

This map (Figure 4) shows the search results for the Onam saree region wise. The number of search results are more concentrated in Kerala, Puducherry, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka in descending order of search results. This is a signal to the producers of this state to increase their production of the Onam saree since it is a popular product among citizens of these

states. The highest number of search results in Kerala can be explained by the fact that Onam is a festival that has originated from Kerala [11] and is most celebrated there.

Figure 5: Search results for Veshti over 3 years

The search results for Veshti in Figure 5 remain fairly active during the entirety of the year making it a popular product year-round. The peaks are experienced especially during the month of October which signals producers to increase their output and maybe even increase their prices due to the increase in demand. This is a signal to the producers to increase their production of Veshti during the month of October. This can be explained by the fact that the festival of Puratasi is celebrated during this month which is categorised by wearing traditional clothing. [12]

Figure 6: Search results for Veshti region wise

This map (Figure 6) shows the search results for the Veshti region wise. The number of search results are more concentrated in Puducherry, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Kerala in descending order of search results. This is a signal to the producers of this state to increase their production of the Veshti since it is a popular product among citizens of these states. The highest number of search results in TamilNadu and Puducherry can be explained by the fact that it is the traditional clothing item of these two states, thereby worn all year round and being incredibly popular in these states. [13]

Figure 7: Search results for Langa Voni over 3 years

The search results of Langa Voni in Figure 7 remain significantly higher than both Veshti and Onam saree year long. The peak seasons are experienced during October and September making it a very popular product year round because of the festival of Puratasi which includes wearing traditional clothing [13]. Productions are also high because Langa Voni is a traditional clothing of these states. This implies that producers should keep their productions increased throughout the year but increase production especially in the months where a hike in the search results is seen.

Figure 8: Search results for Langa Voni region wise

This map shows the search results for the Langa Voni region wise in Figure 8. The number of search results are more concentrated in Telangana, Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka and Kerala in descending order of search results. This is a signal to the producers of this state to increase their production of the Langa Voni since it is a popular product among citizens of these states. The popularity hike during September and October could be explained by the fact that Vijay Dashmi is celebrated in these states during these months [14].

Figure 9: Search results for Pattu Pavadai over 3 years

The searches for Pattu Pavadai as seen in Figure 9 remain fairly low throughout the year indicating lesser consumer demand for this product. The demand reaches its peak during the months of July recording an all time high in 2022 which shows regaining popularity for this product in the coming years signalling producers to increase their production in the month of July.

Figure 10: Search results for Pattu Pavadai region wise

This map in Figure 10 shows the search results for the Pattu Pavadai region. The number of search results are more concentrated in Kerala, TamilNadu and Puducherry in descending order of search results. This is a signal to the producers of this state to increase their production of the Pattu Pavadai since it is a popular product among citizens of these states. The popularity hike in July can be explained by the fact that Vyasa Puja is celebrated during this time [15].

Discussion

Figure 11: explaining supply and demand

This can also be explained by the demand (here explained by the search results) and supply diagram shown above in Figure 11. When the demand of a product increases, the demand curve shifts rightwards from D to D1. Since there is a disequilibrium in the market because of this, an upward pressure is exerted on price and the price increases from P* (equilibrium price) to P1 and Optimum quantity increases from Q* (Equilibrium quantity) to Q1. P1 x Q1 is now the new equilibrium in the market for a particular product. This is a signal to producers and an incentive for them to increase their production since the prices have increased. This explains the change in demand during the peak season and how the producers should react to it.

On the other hand, when the demand (explained by the search results) falls during the off season, that is shifting of the demand curve from D to D2. Since there is a disequilibrium in the market because of this, a downward pressure is exerted on price and the price decreases from P* (equilibrium price) to P2 and Optimum quantity decreases from Q* (Equilibrium quantity) to Q2. P2 x Q2 is now the new equilibrium in the market for a particular product. This is a signal to producers and an incentive to them to scale back their output,

avoiding overstocking and potential losses.

Thus, the graph encapsulates the cyclical nature of market forces, illustrating how shifts in demand prompt corresponding adjustments in production to restore market equilibrium. Utilising this knowledge, producers can maximise their profits by producing those products whose demand is greatest in the market at a particular point in time.

Figure 12: Combination of all results

These results show that even though the demand for the Onam saree remains fairly lower than all the other products being compared, it is also one whose demand peaks the most during the festive season. The demand for Pattu Pavadai has been increasing over time with its demand peaking during July. Search results for Veshti remain consistently and comparatively low year round as compared to the other goods. The demand for Langa Voni also remains consistently low throughout the year but not as low as Veshti and Onam saree (in the off season).

The patterns observed in the search results can be attributed to cultural and religious festivals that influence the demand for traditional clothing. For example, the surge in searches for

Onam saree and Veshti aligns with the respective festivals in August-September and October, emphasising the cultural significance attached to these garments during festive seasons.

The consistently high search results for Langa Voni reflect its year-round popularity, deeply rooted in cultural traditions. The increased interest during the months of September and October correlates with the Vijay Dashmi celebrations in states like Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, and Kerala.

Pattu Pavadai's lower overall search volumes suggest a relatively lower demand, but the spike in July indicates a potential resurgence in popularity. The association with the Puratasi festival during this time may be driving increased interest in this traditional attire.

For Onam saree producers, understanding the seasonal nature of demand is crucial. While the overall demand might be lower, the significant peak during the festival season provides an opportunity for targeted marketing campaigns and limited-edition collections. Collaborations with influencers and cultural ambassadors can help generate buzz leading up to the festival, maximising sales during the peak period.

Pattu Pavadai producers should capitalise on the increasing demand trend by investing in production capacity and marketing efforts. Recognizing the spike in July, aligning promotional activities with the Puratasi festival can enhance visibility and consumer engagement. Innovations in design and materials can also contribute to sustaining and expanding this upward demand trajectory.

Veshti producers face the challenge of consistently low demand throughout the year. Exploring rebranding strategies, associating Veshti with contemporary fashion trends, or highlighting its cultural significance through storytelling can help reposition it in the market. Collaborations with fashion designers or influencers can bring a fresh perspective, potentially increasing its appeal among a broader audience.

Langa Voni producers should leverage the steady year-round demand by ensuring a consistent supply. While the demand may not peak significantly, sustaining a steady market presence is valuable. Exploring collaborations with cultural events or influencers from regions with a historical affinity for Langa Voni can help broaden its appeal.

The research results provide valuable insights into consumer behaviour and preferences, enabling industry stakeholders to make informed decisions to meet the dynamic demands of the market. By aligning production and marketing strategies with cultural and festival-driven trends, producers can enhance their competitiveness and cater effectively to the diverse and evolving preferences of consumers.

4. Limitations

Firstly, the availability and reliability of historical data for fashion trends, especially for traditional clothing and handicraft markets, may be a challenge. Incomplete or inconsistent data can impact the accuracy of the analysis. Moreover search results from google may not represent the actual state of popularity for a product in the real world market. This can be addressed by conducting primary research through surveys, interviews, or collaborations with local artisans and fashion experts can supplement existing data and provide a more comprehensive understanding of trends.

Secondly, regional heterogeneity can arise as the cultural and fashion preferences can vary significantly across different regions within the same state. This can be resolved by subdividing regions within states for a more granular analysis that can offer a deeper understanding of regional variations in fashion trends, providing insights that might be overlooked in a broader state-level analysis.

Lastly, seasonal variations in data may be influenced by factors beyond fashion trends, such as festivals or special events. Distinguishing between genuine fashion trends and season-specific cultural practices can be challenging. A more holistic analysis can be done by collaborating with local experts and incorporating qualitative data can help contextualise seasonal trends, providing a more nuanced interpretation of the impact of different seasons on fashion markets.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research paper delved into the intricate dynamics of the traditional clothing and handicraft market, with a focus on the seasonal variations in demand. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from Google Trend searches with qualitative insights, to analyse the popularity trends of four specific clothing types in southern India over a two-year post-Covid-19 period.

The results revealed distinctive patterns in the demand for Onam saree, Veshti, Langa Voni, and Pattu Pavadai, each influenced by cultural festivals and traditions. The research demonstrated that understanding the seasonality in the handicraft market is crucial for producers to maximise profits and minimise seasonal unemployment. By aligning production

and marketing strategies with cultural and festival-driven trends, producers can cater effectively to the diverse and evolving preferences of consumers.

Looking ahead, future perspectives involve addressing limitations such as data availability and reliability, regional heterogeneity, and the impact of seasonal fluctuations. Opportunities lie in conducting primary research to supplement existing data, subdividing regions for a more granular analysis, and collaborating with local experts to contextualise seasonal trends. By overcoming these challenges, the traditional clothing and handicraft industry can continue to thrive, preserving cultural heritage, and providing sustainable livelihoods for artisans.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my heartfelt appreciation to my economics teacher, Ms. Sahana G Rao. I extend my sincere gratitude for instilling in me a passion for Economics and providing valuable insights that have significantly influenced the content and analysis presented in this paper. I am deeply thankful to my parents for their unending love, encouragement, and understanding.

References

1. Sridhar, A. (2023, February 7). *Role and importance of Indian handicraft industry*. RTF | Rethinking The Future. <https://www.re-thinkingthefuture.com/architectural-community/a9287-role-and-importance-of-indian-handicraft-industry/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.
2. *Indian handicrafts, Best Handicraft products manufacturers in India - IBEF*. India Brand Equity Foundation. (n.d.). <https://www.ibef.org/exports/handicrafts-industry-india>. Accessed 28 December 2023.
3. *Handicraft market size, share: Growth Analysis Report [2030]*. Handicraft Market Size, Share | Growth Analysis Report [2030]. (n.d.). <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/handicraft-market-108435>. Accessed 28 December 2023.
4. Group, I. (n.d.). *Indian handicrafts market size, share, analysis, report 2023-2028*. Indian Handicrafts Market Size, Share, Analysis, Report 2023-2028. <https://www.imarcgroup.com/india-handicrafts-market>. Accessed 28 December 2023.
5. Indian handicraft industry. (n.d.). <http://www.jhea.in/indian-handicraft-industry>. Accessed 29 December 2023

6. Dalal, A., & Chattopadhyay, S. (2022). A preliminary study on popularising Indian handicrafts using internet technology – A Bengal specific study. *Atlantis Highlights in Social Sciences, Education and Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/ahsseh.k.220105.007>. Accessed 29 December 2023
7. Kumar, P. A. (n.d.). *Trend reports and seasonal collections in the handmade industry*. Rural Handmade. <https://ruralhandmade.com/blog/trend-reports-and-seasonal-collections-in-the-handmade>. Accessed 29 December 2023
8. Gracie@qckbot.com. (2023, September 27). *Google trends: How it can help with market research*. QCKBOT. Accessed 29 December 2023
9. Google. (n.d.). *The shifting seasonal demand for fashion - think with google*. Google. <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-emea/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/shifting-fashion-demand-spring-summer/>. Accessed 29 December 2023
10. *Onam Saree Styles : Modern Twists on Traditional Drapes*, The Loom, 18 August 2023, <https://www.theloom.in/blog/?p=9793>. Accessed 27 November 2023.
11. “Onam- All About the 10 Days Harvest Festival and Celebrations.” *Asia Highlights, Asian Highlights*, 23 October 2023, <https://www.asiahighlights.com/india/onam>. Accessed 27 November 2023.
12. Govindarajulu, Rajesh. “Puratasi Shanikizhamai Pooja.” *The Verandah Club*, The Verandah Club, <https://theverandahclub.com/article/puratasi-shanikizhamai-pooja-407>. Accessed 27 11 2023.
13. Azam, Shuaib. “The Rich Cultural Heritage of Tamil Nadu Traditional Dress: A Complete Guide.” *Hubble Money*, 27 September 2023, <https://www.myhubble.money/blog/the-rich-cultural-heritage-of-tamil-nadu-traditional-dress-a-complete-guide>. Accessed 27 November 2023.
14. Caiazza, T. (2023, August 14). *Vijayadashami*. National Today. <https://nationaltoday.com/vijayadashami/>. Accessed 27 November 2023.
15. *Home*. Tamil Calendar 2024, July. (n.d.). <https://www.prokerala.com/general/calendar/tamilcalendar.php?year=2024&month=july&sb=1#calendar>. Accessed 27 November 2023.